

Open Science NL

Open Research Software and FAIR Data Advisory Panel

Meeting Agenda

18 May 2026, 15:00-17:00

Location: [MS Teams](#)

Attendees

- Ana Martinovici
- Andrew S. Hoffman
- Bogdana Huma
- Daniel S. Katz
- Efi Gkoumassi
- Erik van den Bergh – from 16.00
- Iza Witkowska
- Martine de Vos
- Morane Gruenpeter
- Santosh Ilamparuthi
- Thomas Pronk
- Mark van Assem (MvA), Acting Co-Chair
- Marta Teperek (MT), Chair

Agenda

15.00 - 15.05 – Welcome and agenda

15.05 – 16.00 – Introductions and getting to know each other

3 minutes each:

- Who are you (name, affiliation)?
- What's the expertise/experience you are bringing to the panel?
- What are, in your opinion, the two biggest challenges pertaining to open research software, FAIR data or open research hardware, which could be addressed by Open Science NL in the upcoming years?
- Any potential conflicts of interest you wish to declare.

16.00 – 16.40 - Expertise of panel members

In preparation for the first meeting of the merged Open Research Software and FAIR Data Advisory Panel, the expertise of the Open Research Software and FAIR Data Advisory Panels was merged into one document *Profiles and Terms of reference*. Panel members are asked to review that document (and the relevant notes of the panel meetings) and discuss if any expertise is currently missing in that document (or if anything should be merged/rephrased/removed).

Secondly, based on the content of the introductory presentations, panel members are asked to elaborate on the following:

- Is the expertise covered by existing panel members, or do new panel members need to be appointed?
 - o Note that it is already clear that it will be essential to appoint someone representing the Universities of Applied Sciences and a knowledge/research institute.

16.40 – 16.45 – Changes to the Terms of Reference

Terms of reference document was changed to reflect that the panels were merged and also to add a sentence about removal of panel members in case of repeated absences (as discussed during the last panel meetings). Panel members are asked to indicate if any additional changes to the Terms of Reference need to be made.

16.45 – 16.50 - Name of the panel

Given the expanded scope of the merged panel, the name of the panel should also change. Based on the suggestions made in the last Open Research Software and FAIR Data panel meetings, it is proposed that the new panel is simply called “Open Research Software and FAIR Data Advisory Panel”. Panel members are asked to raise any potential objections to the proposed name.

16.50 – 16.55 – Next meeting

During the next panel meeting (12 October 2026, 15.00 – 17.00, hybrid) the following will be discussed:

- Term duration of panel members
- Selection of new members from the applications received

16.55 – 17.00: AOB and meeting close